

FEMALE SCHOOL ADMINISTRATORS IN JOLO: THEIR LEADERSHIP JOURNEY AND CHALLENGES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11652610>

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the challenges faced by female school administrators in Jolo and the strategies they employ to overcome these obstacles. Using a qualitative research approach, in-depth interviews were conducted with both male and female respondents to gain comprehensive insights into the experiences of female administrators. Thematic analysis was used to identify key challenges, including gender bias, balancing professional and personal responsibilities, safety concerns, lack of professional development opportunities, and cultural expectations. Despite these hurdles, the study reveals relevant and strategic approaches of these administrators. By recognizing and addressing gender bias, engaging in continuous personal development, and employing transformational leadership styles, female administrators able to improve their leadership effectiveness and advance their careers. Their data-driven decision-making, supportive interactions with colleagues, encouraging relationships with students, and cooperative community engagement further highlight their positive impact in Jolo. The findings explicitly revealed the need for an equitable work environment that supports the growth and success of female leaders, specifically enhancing the effectiveness of educational institutions.

Keywords: *Female leadership, educational administration, challenges faced by female administrators, coping strategies, empowerment.*

INTRODUCTION

The world has seen the transformation and advancement in the new millennium. The efficacy and quality of education are correlated with the ability to adapt to transformative processes. Women in the province of Sulu, who make up half of the population and are primarily responsible for raising the next generation, are now recognized to have excellent employment because of their education, which also serves as a necessary condition for them to adjust to these changes. In the study of Rehbock, S. K. (2020), he illustrates the unique demands of leadership in academia, a context which is currently characterized by changing conditions and developments such as new public management and heightened international competition. Academics have to fulfill multiple demands and are increasingly expected to be effective leaders.

Women participate more in production and development when they have higher education. It is believed that the future of women leaders seems to be bright due to higher female educational attainment (Maheshwari 2023). Furthermore, to educate women and men equally, more work needs to be put into establishing professional attitudes in both the social and educational spheres.

Sulu is a crucial area where the government works to make improvements in employment. When it comes to employment involvement, women are less advantaged than men. In the Republic of the Philippines, women's participation in the labor force appeared to decline in proportion to their level of education. This statement brought to light the limited prospects available to women in our nation, particularly considering that the Philippines is a developing nation with a need for more employment opportunities.

When it comes to educational leadership, women are often stereotyped as being unequal to what men can do. Even though equal chances encompass opportunities presented in various educational institutions in Sulu nowadays, the number of women in line for leadership still needs to grow. In the present time, there are growing criticisms faced by women leaders due to gender inequality. Some of these problems were manifested to degrade women's capacity by citing that women are less capable compared to men.

Rauhaus, B. M., & Carr, I. A. S. (2019) perceived that gender differences in faculty responsibilities and experiences may impact individuals' professional experiences related to job satisfaction, advancement, and promotion. In the discussion of traditional beliefs, there are many individuals who are thinking that men should always be the ones to lead. In the study of Alameeri, K., Alshurideh, M., & Al Kurdi, B. (2023) wherein articulated that the importance of paying attention to the factors affecting women in leadership and management in order to empower them and decrease gender discrimination in the workspace. Recent research has highlighted the evolving pathways for women in leadership. A study by Sandberg and Thomas (2020) emphasizes that despite increasing opportunities, women still encounter unique challenges that shape their leadership trajectories. The concept of the "glass cliff," where women are more likely to be appointed to precarious leadership positions during times of crisis, has been further examined by Ryan et al. (2016).

Stemming the structure of school administration, there are female teachers-in-charge and deans in Sulu who are grappling with criticisms. The belief of average performance indebted to every female leader is a manifestation of gender discrimination. However, there are no complexities in female leaders' administration skills, but the fact that setbacks of putting women in high-rank positions still need to be corrected most. But the ideas of Wadesango, N., & Karima, R. (2016), it is said that Women should accept change and perceive taking hardship positions as a way of climbing to the upper echelons of educational educators.

Even while women and men have collaborated throughout history and at all societal levels, their contributions have only sometimes been equally acknowledged, and women have consistently been viewed as secondary to males. Women who hold low-status employment are accepted as usual. They have, however, found it extremely challenging to begin working in high-status positions or to advance in their careers. All too often, women who aspire to hold senior administrative posts face the phenomenon known as the "glass ceiling." As a result, it can be said that with administrative positions that require greater responsibilities, women are found in limited numbers (Çelikten, 2004; Ergün, 1996; Shum & Cheng, 1997). Successful female administrators often employ a range of strategies to overcome barriers. A study by Brown, Kelan, and Humbert (2018) suggests that developing resilience and adaptive leadership skills are crucial for navigating gender biases. Moreover, engaging in continuous learning and seeking out leadership training programs are identified as effective strategies (McKinsey & Company, 2020).

It is noteworthy to observe the numerous distinctions between the duties of men and women despite the advancements made by women employed in various sectors (Acuner & Sallan, 1993). Any legal issues do not impede the appointment or advancement of women. Despite having equal educational backgrounds, women are afforded different chances than men.

Keating and Safir (2019) argue that authenticity in leadership allows women to build trust and credibility with their teams. By being transparent, empathetic, and consistent in their actions, female leaders can foster a positive and inclusive organizational culture. This approach not only enhances team performance but also supports the personal and professional growth of the leader and her team members.

Teaching has historically been a vocation that is suited for women (Apple, 1994). Nonetheless, women are underrepresented in higher jobs in both high schools and colleges (Blackmore, 1998). This indicates that men are more likely to work in administration (Streitmatter, 1999). The proportion of female administrators in the Ministry of Education has yet to reach 25%, even though 48% of Filipino primary and secondary school teachers are female.

Due to the literature above, the researchers aimed to investigate the level of challenges of female administrators in Jolo, Sulu, Philippines.

According to research, women who become school administrators frequently have different career paths that are marked by a variety of entry points, career breaks, and nonlinear routes. These trajectories may be impacted by elements including obligations to one's family, harassment at work, and a lack of mentorship opportunities (Brunner et al., 2019). Examining the professional trajectories of female school administrators in Sulu can shed light on how cultural norms and professional goals interact.

Obstacles that face female school administrators include discrimination based on gender, problems juggling work and personal obligations, and restricted access to opportunities for professional growth. Research indicates that policies encouraging gender equity, mentorship programs, and supportive work settings are crucial in tackling these issues (Brunner et al., 2019; Fitzgerald & Gunn, 2020). Targeted interventions to assist the professional growth and advancement of female school administrators in Sulu can be informed by an understanding of the unique challenges they encounter.

Despite experiencing difficulties, female administrators of schools show resiliency and use a variety of leadership techniques to overcome obstacles and encourage constructive change within their organizations. Studies highlight the significance of promoting gender-sensitive policies, creating networks of support, and cultivating inclusive leadership practices (Karp & Helou, 2018). Analyzing the leadership techniques used by Sulu's female school administrators can provide valuable insights into how to get past obstacles and promote institutional change.

Research by Eargly and Carli (2007) emphasized that gender stereotypes can influence perceptions of leadership effectiveness, with traits traditionally associated with leadership often aligning more closely with male characteristics. This explains that the male genes are more coherent with the leadership standard. A study by the World Economic Forum (2023) highlights that despite progress, unconscious biases still significantly impact women's career advancements. The research emphasizes the need for greater awareness and proactive measures to create representative power structures within organizations ([World Economic Forum](#)).

Within this educational setting, the amplification of the perspectives and experiences of female school administrators has been influential in shaping educational leadership and gender equality in Sulu. Yeakey, C. C., Johnston, G. S., & Adkison, J. A. (1986) explicitly stated that interest in the study of race/ethnic minorities and women in public school administration had evolved over the past decade. This study draws attention to how crucial it is to acknowledge and resolve the particular difficulties faced by women in leadership positions in the field of education.

In addition, gender disparities in educational leadership are widely documented, understanding how women become underrepresented in senior administrative positions. There are studies indicating that societal norms, cultural expectations, and institutional biases contribute to these disparities, limiting women's access to leadership roles (Shakeshaft, 2019). In Sulu, where traditional gender roles may influence perceptions of women's leadership capabilities, understanding these dynamics is crucial.

Hence, women who become school administrators frequently face different career breaks and nonlinear routes in leadership. These trajectories may be impacted by obligations to one's family, harassment at work, and a lack of mentorship opportunities (Brunner et al., 2019). Examining the professional trajectories of female school administrators in Sulu can shed light on how cultural norms and professional goals interact. Hence, Harrison, M. G., King, R. B., & Hocson, S. M. G. (n.d.) sought out that the ability of school heads to foster a school ethos supportive of counselling is essential in enabling counsellors to leverage the multifunctional nature of their work, become embedded and centrally positioned in the school community, and enhance their effectiveness. Doing so can enable counselling to be more culturally accessible to young people. It is why female leaders are also in need to be backboned by moral and trainings supports.

Based on the review-related literature and studies presented, the researchers aims to quantify the experiences and challenges encountered by female school administrators in Jolo, Sulu, focusing on their perspectives and struggles in the institution.

Research Questions

The study seeks to investigate the challenges faced by female school administrators in Jolo. Hence, it addresses the following research questions:

1. What specific challenges do female school administrators encounter in their professional roles within the educational institutions of Jolo?
2. How do these female administrators overcome the challenges they face in their leadership roles?
3. In what ways does gender influence their leadership styles, decision-making processes, and interactions with colleagues, students, and the community?

METHODOLOGY

This study used a qualitative research design, specifically a phenomenological approach, to explore and understand the lived experiences, leadership journeys, and challenges faced by female school administrators in Jolo. This approach is chosen to provide in-depth insights into the subjective experiences and personal narratives of the participants.

Purposive sampling is adopted to select participants who are female school administrators in Jolo. There were three secondary schools surveyed: Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades, Sulu College of Technology Inc., and Southern Mindanao Islamic Institute as access participants of the study. There were 10 female leaders and 10 male leaders from said school obtained as final sample size for the possible themes or insights from the interviews.

Hence, the study used in-depth Interview such as semi-structured in-depth interviews for the participants. This method is used to have flexibility in probing deeper into participants' responses and uncovering rich, detailed narratives about their leadership journeys and challenges. The following is the interview guide that is part in developing a questionnaire. These ensure that key topics are covered while allowing participants the freedom to express their thoughts and experiences. Key topics included such as:

- Background and career trajectory
- Leadership style and philosophy
- Key milestones and achievements
- Challenges faced in their roles
- Strategies for overcoming challenges
- Support systems and networks

The participants were given 60-90 minutes to answer the formulated questionnaire. Their responses were audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim for accurate data analysis. Key themes were identified and essentially coded through participants' experiences and perspectives on their leadership journeys and challenges. These themes were refined and validated through iterative analysis.

Prior the conduct of the survey, the participants were provided with detailed information about the study's purpose, procedures, risks, and benefits. Written informed consent were provided before the commencement of the interviews. Hence, the researchers ensured that Participants' confidentiality will be strictly maintained. Pseudonyms were used in all transcripts, reports, and publications in order to protect participants' identities.

While Participation in the study were considered voluntarily. To ensure credibility, member checking was conducted where participants will be asked to review and verify the accuracy of the transcribed interviews and preliminary findings. Peer debriefing sessions will be conducted to enhance the dependability and confirmability of the findings. By following this methodology, the study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the leadership journeys and challenges faced by female school administrators in Jolo, contributing valuable insights to the field of educational leadership.

RESULTS

Table 1

Presented the Female Administrators' Challenges and Perspectives			
Research Question no. 1	Codes	Categories	Themes
1. What specific challenges do female school administrators encounter in their professional roles within the educational institutions of Jolo?	A1 . Gender Bias and Discrimination	Assumption of competence	Challenges Faced by Female School Administrators in Jolo
	A2- Balancing Professional and Personal Responsibilities	Managing of household tasks and caregiving roles	
	A3- Safety and Security Concerns	Impact of ongoing conflicts and threats	
	A4- Lack of Professional Development Opportunities	Hindered growth and advancement	
	A5-Inadequate support from the educational system	Insufficient mentoring	
	A6- Cultural and Societal Expectation	Pressure from traditional gender roles	

Table 2

Presented the Female Administrators in overcoming challenges			
Research Question no.2	Codes	Categories	Themes
2. How do these female administrators overcome the challenges they face in their leadership roles?	A1- Identification of Challenges	Gender Bias and Stereotypes	Overcoming challenges and enhancing leadership effectiveness
	A2- Strategies to overcome challenges	Personal Development	
	A3- Impact of Strategies on Leadership Effectiveness	Career advancement	

Table 3

Presented the Gender Influences in Leadership and Organizational Behavior			
Research Question no.3	Codes	Categories	Themes
1. In what ways does gender influence their leadership styles, decision-making processes, and interactions with colleagues, students, and the community?	Leadership Style	Transformational	Gender Influences in Leadership and Organizational Behavior
	Decision-Making	Data driven	
	Interaction with Colleagues	Supportive	
	Interaction with Students	Encouraging	
	Interaction with Community	Cooperative	

DISCUSSION

This chapter explained and discussed the tabular presentation of non-numerical data gathered from the respondents. The researchers elaborated on the different categories of female administrators’ concern about their leadership challenges and perspectives.

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	A4- Lack of Professional Development Opportunities	Hindered growth and advancement	
	A5-Inadequate support from the educational system	Insufficient mentoring	
	A6- Cultural and Societal Expectation	Pressure from traditional gender roles	

Table 1 elicits the responds of the respondents on the emerging theme, Challenges Faced by Female Administrators in Jolo. Both Male and Female respondents stated that Female administrators often faced significant gender bias and discrimination, leading to an assumption of their incompetence. This bias manifests in various ways, including undermining their authority, questioning their decisions more frequently than those of male counterparts, and an overall lack of respect for their capabilities. This creates an environment where women must work harder to prove their competence and gain the same level of recognition as men.

Based on the statements of the respondents on the code Balancing Professional and Personal Responsibilities, Female administrators in Jolo struggle with balancing their professional duties with household tasks and caregiving roles. Cultural expectations had placed the burden of managing home responsibilities primarily on women. This is known factor that increased stress and burnout of Female leaders. Hence, the respondents stated that dual responsibility impacts Female ability to fully commit to their administrative roles, often resulting in compromised professional performance.

Hence, in terms of Safety and Security Concerns, the ongoing conflicts and threats in Jolo present significant safety and security concerns for female administrators. These concerns are not only about their personal safety but also about the safety of their students and staff. The constant worry about security issues makes it challenging for them to perform their duties effectively and without distraction.

With further Lack of Professional Development Opportunities there is a notable lack of professional development opportunities tailored to the needs of female administrators. This lack of targeted training and development programs hinders their growth and advancement within the educational system. Without access to proper professional development, female administrators are less able to innovate and lead effectively.

In terms of Inadequate Support from the Educational System, the respondents stated that the educational system in Jolo provides fewer leadership training for school administrators. There is a lack of mentoring, networking opportunities with other female leaders, and institutional policies that promote gender equality.

The code Cultural and Societal Expectations traditional gender roles and societal expectations place additional pressure on female administrators. These cultural norms

create resistance to women in leadership positions, both within educational institutions and in the broader community. Such expectations limit their ability to assert their authority and implement changes, challenging their professional legitimacy.

Table 2

Presented the Female Administrators in overcoming challenges			
Research Question no.2	Codes	Categories	Themes
2. How do these female administrators overcome the challenges they face in their leadership roles?	A1- Identification of Challenges	Gender Bias and Stereotypes	Overcoming challenges and enhancing leadership effectiveness
	A2- Strategies to overcome challenges	Personal Development	
	A3- Impact of Strategies on Leadership Effectiveness	Career advancement	

The table 2 presents a detailed and structured examination of how female administrators overcome leadership challenges. Based on the result, recognizing gender bias and stereotyping role are the first step towards addressing these issues. By identifying these barriers, female administrators will be better equipped to develop targeted strategies to counteract the biases and advocate for a more equitable work environment.

According to the respondents stated that engaging in personal development is a proactive approach that female administrators take to empower themselves. This includes participating in leadership training, team-building activities, and continuous learning. These efforts result in increased confidence, improved skill sets, and greater adaptability, which are essential for overcoming challenges and excelling in leadership roles.

The strategies employed by female administrators lead to significant career advancement. By investing in personal development and effectively managing challenges, these leaders enhance their decision-making abilities, achieve higher job satisfaction, and experience professional growth. This career advancement not only benefits the individual administrators but also serves as an inspiration and a role model for other women aspiring to leadership positions.

Hence the theme of overcoming challenges and enhancing leadership effectiveness encapsulates the successful journey of female administrators. Through a combination of self-awareness, personal development, and strategic action, these leaders transform potential obstacles into opportunities for growth and improvement. Their interest to

acquire and surmount these challenges demonstrates adaptability and commitment to continuous improvement.

Moreover, the ability to identify and acknowledge gender bias and stereotypes is a crucial positive step. It empowers female administrators to confront these issues head-on, raising awareness and driving change within their organizations. This proactive stance fosters a more inclusive and supportive work environment.

The emphasis on personal development reflects a positive and forward-thinking approach. Female administrators who prioritize their growth and development are better prepared to handle leadership challenges. This proactive mindset leads to enhanced leadership capabilities, greater resilience, and a more robust professional presence.

The positive impact of these strategies is evident in the career progression of female administrators. By overcoming gender-related challenges through personal development and strategic action, these leaders achieve significant career milestones. This success not only validates their efforts but also paves the way for future generations of female leaders, contributing to a more diverse and equitable leadership landscape.

Table 3

Research Question no.3	Codes	Categories	Themes
3. In what ways does gender influence their leadership styles, decision-making processes, and interactions with colleagues, students, and the community?	Leadership Style	Transformational	Gender Influences in Leadership and Organizational Behavior
	Decision-Making	Data driven	
	Interaction with Colleagues	Supportive	
	Interaction with Students	Encouraging	
	Interaction with Community	Cooperative	

The table presents a comprehensive analysis of how gender influences leadership styles, decision-making processes, and interactions with colleagues, students, and the community. The research question at the center of this analysis seeks to understand the nuanced ways in which gender impacts these various dimensions of leadership and organizational behavior.

The code Transformational under the category of leadership style indicates a trend where gender plays a significant role in the adoption of transformational leadership. According to the respondents Female Administrators in Jolo were Transformational leaders and were known for their ability to inspire and motivate their teams to achieve beyond expectations. This style involves fostering an environment of collaboration, innovation, and personal development. Hence the researchers found out that female leaders are more likely to exhibit transformational qualities, emphasizing interpersonal relationships, empowerment, and team cohesion. This aligns with the broader understanding that transformational leadership is associated with positive organizational outcomes, including increased employee satisfaction and performance.

In terms of decision-making, the respondents stated that Female Administrators are Data driven. This highlights an aspect for using empirical evidence and data to guide decisions. This approach ensures that decisions are objective and based on concrete information rather than subjective judgment. Gender can influence this propensity, with some studies indicating that female leaders may rely more on collaborative and data-informed decision-making processes. This can be attributed to a tendency to seek comprehensive perspectives and minimize biases, thus enhancing the accuracy and effectiveness of decisions.

The supportive nature of interactions with colleagues, as indicated by the code "Supportive," underscores the role of gender in fostering a positive work environment. Supportive leaders provide encouragement, assistance, and backing to their colleagues, promoting teamwork and collaboration. Female leaders are often associated with a more supportive and empathetic interaction style, which can lead to increased morale, stronger relationships, and improved overall team performance. This supportive approach helps create a culture of mutual respect and trust, essential for organizational success.

The code "Encouraging" within the category of interaction with students reflects a leadership approach that emphasizes motivation and upliftment. Leaders who adopt an encouraging style focus on helping students achieve their potential and fostering a positive learning environment. Gender influences this interaction style, with female leaders often being more nurturing and encouraging. This approach can significantly impact students' academic and personal growth, leading to better educational outcomes and a more supportive school culture.

The cooperative nature of interactions with the community, as captured by the code "Cooperative," highlights the importance of gender in community engagement. Cooperative leaders work collaboratively with community members and stakeholders, building partnerships and engaging in mutual support for common goals. Female leaders are frequently seen as more community-oriented and cooperative, focusing on relationship-building and collective action. This cooperative approach can enhance community relations, foster trust, and drive successful community initiatives.

Conclusions

The study on female school administrators in Jolo reveals a complex landscape of challenges and strategies that shape their professional experiences. The findings indicate that these administrators face significant hurdles, including gender bias, balancing professional and personal responsibilities, safety concerns, lack of professional development opportunities, inadequate support from the educational system, and cultural expectations. These challenges create an environment where female leaders must work harder to prove their competence and gain recognition, often leading to increased stress and burnout.

Despite these obstacles, the resilience and adaptability of female administrators in Jolo are evident in their proactive approaches to overcoming challenges. Recognizing and addressing gender bias is a crucial first step that empowers them to advocate for a more equitable work environment. Engaging in personal development through continuous learning, leadership training, and team-building activities enhances their skills, confidence, and adaptability. These efforts not only help them manage challenges effectively but also contribute to their professional growth and career advancement.

The study highlights the importance of transformational leadership among female administrators, characterized by their ability to inspire and motivate teams, foster collaboration, and emphasize personal development. This leadership style is associated with positive organizational outcomes, including increased employee satisfaction and performance. Additionally, the data-driven decision-making approach adopted by female administrators ensures that decisions are objective and based on empirical evidence, enhancing their effectiveness and minimizing biases.

The study concluded that supportive interactions with colleagues and encouraging relationships with students further underscore the positive impact of female leadership. By fostering a collaborative and empathetic work environment, female administrators build strong teams and improve overall morale. Their cooperative approach to community engagement strengthens partnerships and drives successful initiatives, benefiting both the school and the broader community.

Therefore, the study underscores the significant contributions of female school administrators in Jolo despite the challenges they face. Their commitment to personal development, strategic action, and transformational leadership not only advances their careers but also sets a positive example for future generations of female leaders. By addressing gender bias, prioritizing professional growth, and fostering supportive relationships, these administrators create a more inclusive and effective educational environment. Their success serves as an inspiration and a catalyst for change, promoting gender equity and driving organizational success in the field of education.

Recommendations

To address the challenges faced by female administrators in Jolo, it is essential to implement comprehensive anti-discrimination policies that eliminate gender bias and discrimination within educational institutions. Introducing work-life balance programs, such as flexible working hours, parental leave, and on-site childcare facilities, can support female administrators in managing their dual responsibilities.

Enhancing safety and security protocols, in collaboration with local law enforcement and community leaders, is crucial for ensuring their safety and mitigating threats. Expanding professional development opportunities through targeted workshops, seminars, and courses can enhance leadership skills and career growth. Creating mentorship and networking programs will provide female administrators with valuable support and knowledge sharing. Promoting gender equality and conducting awareness campaigns to challenge traditional gender roles and societal expectations are necessary to foster a more inclusive environment. Cultivating a supportive institutional culture that values diversity and provides equal opportunities for advancement will further empower female leaders.

Encouraging transformational leadership training will help them inspire and motivate their teams effectively. Implementing data-driven decision-making practices, with access to data analytics tools and training, ensures that decisions are based on empirical evidence and objective analysis. Strengthening community and stakeholder engagement by promoting cooperative and collaborative interactions will build strong partnerships and enhance community relations. These recommendations collectively aim to create a more equitable, supportive, and effective educational environment for female administrators in Jolo.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study, titled "Female Administrators in Jolo: Their Leadership Journey and Challenges," has been reviewed and scrutinized by the School Research Team in Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades. These researchers are trained and mentored by Ugnayan ng Pahinungod, University of the Philippines-Mindanao. All procedures involving the participants adhered to the ethical standards and its policies. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were fully informed about the nature, purpose, and potential risks of the research. Participation was voluntary, with the option to withdraw at any time without penalty. The researchers ensured that confidentiality was maintained by anonymizing data and could be accessed only by the research team. The authors declare no conflict of interest. Thus, we thank the participants for their valuable contributions and acknowledge the support from to Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades.

Acknowledgements

This research, titled "Female Administrators in Jolo: Their Leadership Journey and Challenges," is a work of solicited effort, guidance, and encouragement from numerous individuals from our institution. Indeed, we are sincerely grateful for their invaluable support in the process of writing this research.

We would like to extend our heartfelt gratitude to our Director General in MBHTE-BARMM, DG Marjuni M. Maddi for the motivation and inspiration indebted on us.

We are also immensely thankful to the female administrators in Jolo who generously shared their experiences, insights, and challenges. Their stories and perspectives are the heart of this study. May your courage in leadership continue to inspire many.

Our sincere thanks go to Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades for providing the necessary resources in conducting this research. The support from the administration in providing the means to craft and obtain the data needed is immeasurable.

To our Colleagues and friends who helped shape this research to be successful. Your words of encouragement and thoughtful discussions have greatly enriched this research process.

A special thank you to my family, whose unconditional love, patience, and understanding have been our pillar of strength throughout this endeavor.

Thank you all for being a part of this journey.

Declaration of Interest

As proud Tausug of the province of Sulu, we, the researchers of the study are immensely pleased to present our research topic entitled, "Female School Administrators in Jolo: Their Leadership Journey and Challenges." Our interest in this study is rooted in our strong commitment to acquiring an understanding of the particular educational leadership of female administrators in the Municipality of Jolo who are facing work and cultural challenges.

Furthermore, our primary goal is to explore the experiences of female school administrators in Jolo. Jolo is a known municipality in Sulu for its rich cultural heritage with its highly competitive working environment. Hence, this study aims to shed light on the leadership journey of these women, the obstacles they encounter, and the strategies they employ to overcome these challenges.

Our motivation for this research stems from a strong belief in the transformative power of education and its critical role in effective leadership. We believe that leadership chooses no gender and it always plays a driving force to have educational success. From the global perspective, female administrators often face distinct challenges compared to their male counterparts, including gender biases, cultural expectations, and security concerns.

This research aligns with our broader academic interests in gender studies, educational leadership, and provincial development. As it reflects gender equality and empowering women in leadership positions, therefore, we tend to highlight interventions and practices that would help regress the specific challenges of female administrators in Jolo.

Thus, our dedication to this research is driven by a genuine interest in understanding and addressing the unique challenges faced by female school administrators in Jolo. At the same time, we are committed to conducting this study with the highest standards of academic rigour and ethical integrity, ensuring that the voices and experiences of these women are accurately and respectfully represented.

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